

On the Synthesis of some Thiosemicarbazides and their Transformation to certain 5 membered Heterocycles

Birendra Kumar Paul and U. P. Basu

Several 1-(*p*-sulphamyl) benzoyl-4-substituted thiosemicarbazides and their corresponding oxadiazole, thiadiazole and mercapto-triazole derivatives have been prepared with a view to studying their biological properties.

Various 1-acyl-4-substituted thiosemicarbazide derivatives are known to possess interesting biological properties like antitubercular,¹ antifungal^{1,2} and hypoglycemic³ activities. Even the cyclic compounds such as oxadiazoles, thiadiazoles and mercapto-triazoles, that may be derived from these thiosemicarbazides have also been widely

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3. *Belo. Patent*, 632, 263 (1963); *Chem Abstr*, 1964, 61, 4279.

reported to exhibit antitubercular⁴, bacteriostatic,⁵ hypoglycemic^{6,7} diuretic,⁸ antiviral⁹ and antifungal^{1,10} action. On this basis a systematic study of 1-acyl thiosemicarbazides of the type (II) was considered to be of interest as they themselves may show pharmacodynamic properties as well as may be converted to some oxadiazole (III), thiadiazole (IV) and triazole (V) derivatives of therapeutic importance.

The expected 1-(*p*-sulphamyl) benzoyl 4-substituted thiosemicarbazides (II) were obtained by reacting *p*-sulphamyl benzoyl hydrazine (I) with different substituted isothiocyanates in alcoholic medium according to the method of Silberg and Cosma.¹¹ *p*-sulphamylbenzoyl hydrazine (I) was prepared by the action of hydrazine hydrate on ethyl (*p*-sulphamyl) benzoate, which again was obtained by the oxidation of *p*-toluenesulphonamide with sodium dichromate and subsequent esterification of the resulting acid with ethyl alcohol. The alkyl/aryl isothiocyanates were prepared according to the method of Dains *et al.*¹² The thiosemicarbazides (II), on oxidation with iodine¹¹ in potassium iodide, furnished 2-substituted-5-(*p*-sulphamyl) phenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole (III). Cyclodehydration of (II) with phosphoric acid¹³ gave rise to 2-substituted amino-5-(*p*-sulphamyl) phenyl-1,3,4-thiadiazole (IV). On refluxing with sodium hydroxide¹⁴ (4 per cent) or sodium carbonate (5 per cent) the above thiosemicarbazides (II) furnished 3-(*p*-sulphamyl) phenyl-4-substituted-5-mercapto-1,2,4-4H-triazoles (V). These mercapto-triazoles (V) were also obtained by refluxing *p*-sulphamylbenzoyl hydrazine with alkyl/aryl isothiocyanates in the presence of sodium hydroxide solution (8 per cent) and then acidifying the resulting solution with dilute hydrochloric acid.

EXPERIMENTAL

All melting points are uncorrected.

p-Sulphamyl benzoic acid: This was prepared by the oxidation of *p*-toluenesulphonamide (14.36 g.) with sodium dichromate according to the method of Kamm

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12. F. B. Dains, R. Q. Brewster and C. P. Olander, *Org. Syntheses*, 1926, 6, 72.
13. E. Hoggarth, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 1163.
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and Matthews¹⁵ described for the preparation of *p*-nitrobenzoic acid from *p*-nitrotoluene. It was finally purified by crystallization from boiling water (charcoal). Yield 17 g., m.p. 280–81° (Lit¹⁶ m.p. 280°).

The ethyl ester of the above acid (10 g.) was prepared in the usual way and was finally crystallized from benzene. Yield 14 g., m.p. 112–13° (Lit¹⁶ m.p. 110°).

p-Sulphamylbenzoyl hydrazine: A mixture of ethyl-(*p* sulphamyl) benzoate (10 g.), hydrazine hydrate 60%, 6.5 ml.) and ethanol (95%, 80 ml.) was refluxed for 8 hrs. The solid that separated on cooling the concentrated reaction mixture was filtered off, washed with a little alcohol, then with ether, and dried. It was finally crystallized from boiling water (charcoal). Yield 8 g., m.p. 237–39° (Lit¹⁶ m.p. 230–32°). Found: N, 19.52. Calc. for C₇H₇N₃O₃S: N, 19.54%.

*General method for the preparation of 1-(p-sulphamyl) benzoyl-4-substituted thiosemicarbazides (II)*¹¹: To a suspension of *p*-sulphamylbenzoyl hydrazine (21.5 g., 0.1 mole) in ethanol (95%, 200 ml.) was added the appropriate isothiocyanate (0.12 mole) and the mixture heated under reflux on water bath for 2 hr. The precipitated solid, after cooling, was filtered off, washed with ethanol, dried and finally crystallized from boiling ethanol (or methanol in the case of 4 phenyl derivative). The melting points, yields, molecular formulae and analytical data of the compounds are listed in Table I.

TABLE I

1-(*p*-Sulphamyl)benzoyl-4-substituted thiosemicarbazides (II)

No.	R	M.P. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula	Nitrogen, %	
					Found	Required
1.	C ₂ H ₅	230	85	C ₁₀ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₃ S ₂	18.71	18.55
2.	<i>n</i> -C ₃ H ₇	208–8.5	84	C ₁₁ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₃ S ₂	17.65	17.72
3.	<i>iso</i> -C ₃ H ₇	211	85	C ₁₁ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₃ S ₂	17.88	17.72
4.	<i>n</i> -C ₄ H ₉	201–2	82	C ₁₂ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₃ S ₂	17.39	16.97
5.	Cyclo-C ₆ H ₁₁	211–12	87	C ₁₄ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₃ S ₂	15.94	15.73
6.	C ₆ H ₅	220	89	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₃ S ₂	16.40	16.00

* All the compounds melt with decomposition.

15. O. Kamm and A. O. Matthews, *Org. Syntheses*, 1922, 2, 53.

16. Y. M. Abou-Zeid, A. A. Abou Cuf and H. Ragab, *Bull. Fac. Pharm.*, 1961–62, 1, 169; *Chem. Abstr.*, 1964, 61, 1787.

Action of Iodine¹¹ on (II). Formation of 2-substituted amino-5-(p-sulphamyl) phenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole (III): The appropriate 1-(p-sulphamyl) benzoyl-4-substituted thiosemicarbazide (0.01 mole) was suspended in ethanol (95%, 300 ml.). To this, sodium hydroxide (4 N, 5 ml.) was added with cooling and shaking. To the clear solution, iodine in potassium iodide solution (5%) was added gradually with stirring till the colour of iodine persisted at room temperature. The contents were then heated under reflux on a water bath and more iodine solution added carefully till a permanent tinge of excess iodine remained. The reaction mixture was then poured into ice-cold water (500 ml.) and the precipitated solid filtered off, washed with water and then with warm carbon disulphide. The crude product was finally crystallized from dilute alcohol (charcoal). The compounds thus prepared are listed along with their relevant data in Table II.

TABLE II

2 Substituted amino-5-(p-sulphamyl) phenyl-1, 3, 4-oxadiazoles (III)

No.	R	M.P. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula	Nitrogen, %	
					Found	Required
1.	C ₂ H ₅	244-45	57	C ₁₀ H ₁₂ N ₄ O ₃ S	20.74	20.89
2.	n-C ₃ H ₇	244-45.5 (decomp.)	66	C ₁₁ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₃ S	19.56	19.86
3.	iso-C ₃ H ₇	270-70.5	68	C ₁₁ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₃ S	20.26	19.86
4.	n-C ₄ H ₉	235.5-36.5	59	C ₁₂ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₃ S	19.01	18.92
5.	Cyclo-C ₆ H ₁₁	262(decomp.)	67	C ₁₄ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₃ S	17.73	17.39
6.	C ₆ H ₅	290-91 (decomp.)	72	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ N ₄ O ₃ S	18.00	17.72

Action of phosphoric acid¹³ on (II). Formation of 2-substituted amino 5-(p-sulphamyl) phenyl-1,3,4-thiadiazole (IV): The appropriate thiosemicarbazide (II, 0.02 mole) was added gradually, with stirring during 20 minutes, to syrupy phosphoric acid (85%, 20 ml.) at 120°. The mixture was heated under stirring at this temperature for further 30 minutes and then poured into ice-water (400 ml.) and left overnight. The precipitated solid was filtered off, washed with water and crystallized from ethanol (95%, charcoal) to afford (IV). The acidic filtrate on basification with ammonia gave a small amount of solid which was found to be identical with (IV) in each case. All the thiadiazole derivatives thus prepared are listed in Table III.

TABLE III

2-Substituted amino-5-(*p*-sulphamyl) phenyl-1,3,4,-thiadiazoles (IV)

No.	R	M.P. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula	Nitrogen, %	
					Found	Required
1.	C ₂ H ₅	269.5-70.5	61	C ₁₀ H ₁₂ N ₄ O ₂ S ₂	19.93	19.72
2.	<i>n</i> -C ₃ H ₇	243-44	63	C ₁₁ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₂ S ₂	18.88	18.79
3.	<i>iso</i> -C ₃ H ₇	257-58	65	C ₁₁ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₂ S ₂	18.77	18.79
4.	<i>n</i> -C ₄ H ₉	230-31	62	C ₁₄ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₂ S ₂	17.92	17.95
5.	Cyclo-C ₆ H ₁₁	278-79	67	C ₁₄ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₂ S ₂	16.76	16.57
6.	C ₆ H ₅	283-84	69	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ N ₄ O ₂ S ₂	16.81	16.87

3-(*p*-Sulphamyl) phenyl-4-substituted-5-mercapto-1,2,4-4H-triazole (V): These were prepared by the following two general methods:—

(a) The thiosemicarbazide (II, 0.01 mole) was dissolved in sodium hydroxide solution (4%, 33 ml.) and refluxed gently for 1 hr. The resulting solution was cooled, treated with charcoal and filtered. The filtrate was adjusted to pH 5-6 with dilute hydrochloric acid and the precipitated solid filtered off after cooling, washed with water and crystallized from dilute alcohol (charcoal).

(b) A mixture of *p*-sulphamylbenzoyl hydrazine (I, 0.01 mole) and appropriate isothiocyanate (0.01 mole) was dissolved in sodium hydroxide solution (8%, 17.5 ml.) and refluxed gently for 4 hrs, cooled and filtered. The filtrate was neutralized with dilute hydrochloric acid and the precipitated solid purified and crystallized as in method (a).

The mixture melting points of the compounds prepared by above two methods remained undepressed in each case. Their relevant data are recorded in Table IV.

TABLE IV

3-(*p*-Sulphamyl) phenyl-4-substituted-5-mercapto-1,2,4-4H triazoles (V)

No.	R	M.P. °C	Yield *	Mol. formula	Nitrogen, %	
					Found	Required
1.	C ₂ H ₅	282-83	72	C ₁₀ H ₁₂ N ₄ O ₂ S ₂	19.86	19.72
2.	<i>n</i> -C ₃ H ₇	201-2	77	C ₁₁ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₂ S ₂	18.95	18.79
3.	<i>iso</i> -C ₃ H ₇	279-80	75	C ₁₁ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₂ S ₂	18.98	18.79
4.	<i>n</i> -C ₄ H ₉	169-70	82	C ₁₂ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₂ S ₂	18.20	17.95
5.	Cyclo-C ₆ H ₁₁	235.5-36.5	86	C ₁₄ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₂ S ₂	16.96	16.57
6.	C ₆ H ₅	299-300	91	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ N ₄ O ₂ S ₂	16.90	16.87

* Yield calculated on the basis of the product obtained by method (a).

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